

THE ROLE OF TEACHERS IN FORMING ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS

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Department of Methods of Teaching Exact and Natural Sciences 13.00.02 -
Theory and Methods of Education and Training (Technological Education)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14352142>

Annotation: This article highlights the need to develop entrepreneurial skills of teachers and its importance in the educational process. Methods aimed at forming an entrepreneurial culture in the education system, developing the professional skills and creative abilities of teachers are analyzed. Also, the application of entrepreneurial competence in teaching activities, opportunities for increasing the potential of teachers in this area based on modern innovative approaches are shown. During the study, effective methodological recommendations were developed based on national and foreign experience.

Keywords: Teachers, entrepreneurial skills, innovative approach, professional competence, education system, entrepreneurial culture, pedagogical skills, local and foreign experience.

Introduction.

Today, the education system needs to develop in accordance with modern requirements and changing socio-economic conditions. In this regard, the active participation of teachers not only in organizing the educational process, but also in the formation and application of entrepreneurial skills in practice is becoming one of the pressing issues. Entrepreneurship culture is recognized as one of the main factors not only of economic development, but also of creative thinking and problem-solving abilities.

By developing teachers' entrepreneurial skills, it is possible to increase their professional competence, improve the quality of education, and stimulate creativity in students. The use of innovative approaches in modern education and the study of national and international experiences will lead to effective results in this direction. This article examines the importance of the issue of forming teachers' entrepreneurial competence, methodological foundations, and strategies aimed at its development.

The formation of entrepreneurial skills is an important component of today's modern education system. Teachers should be shown in their activities not only as educators, but also as initiative, creative, and effective problem-

solving approaches. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to use special methods and tools that develop entrepreneurial competence in the educational process.

Entrepreneurial competence includes the following abilities of a teacher:

Creative thinking and innovative approach: proposing new approaches to solving problems, developing and implementing new ideas.

Organizational skills: effective planning and management of the educational process.

Financial literacy: proper allocation and management of financial resources in the educational process.

Teamwork skills: effective communication with students, parents and other colleagues.

The following methods and approaches can be used in the educational process to develop these skills:

Entrepreneurship trainings and seminars: developing entrepreneurial skills in teachers by organizing practical exercises for them.

Case-study (case analysis): performing practical exercises based on real problems, developing problem-solving strategies.

Project-based learning: creating and implementing projects aimed at developing students' creative and initiative abilities.

Use of innovative technologies: introduction of digital platforms, virtual laboratories and other modern tools into the practical activities of teachers.

National and foreign experience suggests a number of effective approaches to the formation of entrepreneurial skills. For example, in European countries, special courses and programs have been developed to improve the professional skills of teachers in entrepreneurship, while in Uzbekistan modern approaches are being introduced in this regard. In particular, projects aimed at developing entrepreneurship based on the "Teacher-Student" principle are being effectively used in the educational process.

Thus, through the formation of entrepreneurial competence, it is possible to increase the effectiveness of teachers' professional activities, take the educational process to a new level, and contribute to the personal development of students.

Discussion:

The formation of entrepreneurial skills of teachers is an important factor in the development of the education system and its adaptation to modern requirements. This process serves not only to improve the professional skills of teachers, but also to develop creative thinking and initiative in students.

Analysis shows that entrepreneurial competence provides the following advantages in the work of teachers:

Creating a creative environment: Teachers with entrepreneurial skills introduce creative and innovative approaches to the teaching process. This increases student interest and improves the quality of education.

Developing independent decision-making skills: Integrating entrepreneurial activities into the work of teachers increases their ability to think independently and make decisions.

Developing socio-economic skills: The modern education system sees teachers not only as providers of knowledge, but also as individuals who feel economic and social responsibility. Entrepreneurial skills play an important role in this regard.

Some problems are also observed in the process of developing entrepreneurial competence in the national education system. In particular:

Lack of special courses and resources for training teachers in entrepreneurship;

Difficulties in introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process;

Insufficient attention is paid to improving the financial literacy of teachers.

Nevertheless, positive developments are being observed in the education system of Uzbekistan in this regard. In particular, effective work is being carried out to organize special advanced training courses and trainings for teachers, develop the "Teacher-Student" tradition, and introduce national and international experiences.

In conclusion, the formation of entrepreneurial skills of teachers is a key factor in increasing the competitiveness of the education system and creating a foundation for the future success of students. Support and integral integration of national and international experiences in this area can accelerate positive changes in the field of education.

Conclusion.

The results of this study show that the formation of entrepreneurial skills of teachers is of great importance in the development of a modern education system. Teachers with entrepreneurial competence not only organize a high-quality educational process, but also help develop students' creativity, initiative and practical skills. The use of innovative technologies in the formation of these skills, enrichment of the educational process through design and practical exercises provides effective results.

During the analysis, the following practical recommendations were developed for the development of entrepreneurial skills based on national and international experiences:

Organize special advanced training courses for teachers on entrepreneurship and financial literacy;

Widespread introduction of innovative technologies and methods in the education system;

Integration of national and international experiences to support the professional development of teachers;

Development of projects based on the “teacher-student” principle and formation of an entrepreneurial culture in the educational process.

In conclusion, by developing the entrepreneurial skills of teachers, it is possible to improve the quality of education, stimulate the creative abilities of students and lay the foundation for their socio-economic success in the future. A systematic approach and continuous support in this direction will ensure the competitiveness of the education sector.

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